

Supplementary information

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Appendix A - Additional material and methods

A.1 - Collect and series of operation on species occurrences

Databases collection:

- Access to source databases:
 - o French Natural and Landscape Information System (SINP, <https://inpn.mnhn.fr>), each of the three study sites has its own database: <https://sinp-occitanie.fr/atlas/> for Lodévois-Larzac (T1), <https://obv-na.fr/> and <https://observatoire-fauna.fr/> for La Rochelle (T2), <https://data.biodiversite-bretagne.fr> for Brocéliande (T3).
 - o GBIF: GBIF.org (04 October 2022) GBIF Occurrence Download <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.ry6uw7>
 - o French biodiversity monitoring scheme (Vigie Nature): <https://www.vigienature.fr/>, the database used are the STOC for Aves, the Vigie-Chiro for Chiroptera and Orthoptera, the Vigie-Flore for Flora, the STELI for Odonata, the STERF for Papilionidae
- Period of 11 years, from 01/01/2010 to 31/12/2020
- Extent: continental France (without island, Corsica and overseas regions)
- Spatial accuracy of 0 to 50m

Standardization of species names : French taxonomic reference TAXREF.V14 (Gargominy et al., 2021).

- Keep only the species and subspecies
- Groups data at the species level

Taxonomic filtering: from TAXREF.V14

- Keep only species in nine taxonomic groups selected: Amphibia, Aves, Chiroptera, Flora, Mammalia aptera (Mammalia), Orthoptera, Odonata, Papilionidae and Reptilia
- Delete species not present in France so keep: "Present", "Endemic", "Subendemic", "Cryptogenic", "Introduced", "Invasive introduced"

Data transformation and filtering:

- Transformation data into occurrence, i.e. transform data into presence only
- Geographical filtering for reduce sampling biases and delete duplicate data: spatial thinning at a distance of 50m with "spThin" package (Aiello-Lammens et al., 2015)

Identify the presence of species into each study site: at least five observations from all databases in the study site to certify the presence of the species

Standardization of the observation period between databases: for Aves filtering observations between 1 March and 15 July corresponding to the STOC period.

A.2 - Environmental variables selected for Species Distribution Models (SDM) of Aves and Papilionidae species. Variables used for SDM are the variables with collinearity removed (Pearson >0.7).

Type of variables		Variables	Database	Year	Raw precision	Source	Variables used for SDM
Geography	Climatic	19 bioclimatic variables	Chelsa	1981-2010	1 km	Karger et al., 2021, 2017	Bio 2 (temp. range), Bio 5 (temp. warmest month), Bio 6 (min. temp. coldest month), Bio 9 (temp. driest quarter), Bio 13 (prec. wettest month), Bio 14 (prec. driest month), Bio 15(prec. seasonality)
	Elevation	Elevation, mean in a buffer of fifty meters	BD ALTI, IGN	2014	25 m	IGN, 2022	Elevation
		Slope, mean in a buffer of 50 meters					Slope
		Topographic Position Index (TPI), mean in a buffer of 50 meters					TPI
	Wetland	Area of wetland potential: very high in a buffer of 50, 500, 2000 meters	INRAE Wetland potential	2014	50 m	Berthier et al., 2014	Wetland in buffer of 50 and 500 m
Waterway	Linear meters of waterway in a buffer of 50, 500, 2000 meters	BD TOPO, IGN	2022	Vector	IGN, 2022	Waterway in buffer of 50 and 500m	
Human occupancy	Land-use	Area of artificial, conifer forest, crop, deciduous forest, land, lawn, mineral, prairie, water in buffer of 50, 500 and 2000 meters	OSO Land Cover	2018	25 m	Inglada et al., 2019	Artificial, conifer, crops, deciduous, fruit culture, land, mineral, prairie, water in a buffer of 50 and 500 m Lawn in a buffer of 500 m, Sand in a buffer of 50, 500, 2000 m
	Hedge line	Linear meters of hedge in a buffer of 50, 500, 2000 meters	BD TOPO, IGN	2022	Vector	IGN, 2022	Hedge line in buffer of 50, 500 m
	NDVI mean	NDVI mean in buffer of 50, 500, 2000 meters	DHI NDVI	2022	10 m	CESBIO, 2021, 2022	DHI NDVI in buffer of 50 and 500m
Pollution / Fragmentation	Light pollution	Mean value in buffer of 500 meters of night time light average masked of 2015	VIIRS night time lights	2015	500 m	Elvidge et al., 2021	Night time light
	Road fragmentation	Linear meters of fragmenting of main road in a buffer of 50, 500, 2000 meters	BD TOPO, IGN	2022	Vector	IGN, 2022	Main road in a buffer of 50, 500, 2000 m

A.3 - Species traits of Aves and Papilionidae. Missing traits were imputed by considering evolutionary relationships following the process of Carmona et al. (2021) with the help the R scripts of Toussaint et al. (2021).

	Traits	Description	Reference
Aves	Mass	Body mass using data from males, females, and/or unspecified adults in g	Storchová and Hořák, 2018
	HWI	Avian hand-wing index (HWI), an estimate of wing shape as a proxy for dispersal ability in birds	Sheard et al., 2020
	Nocturn	Nocturnal activity	Wilman et al., 2014
	Habitats (Deciduous Coniferous, Woodland, Shrub, Grassland, Mountain meadows, Reed, Swamps, Rocks, Urban)	Species occupies habitat in breeding area, 1: yes; 0: no	Storchová and Hořák, 2018
	Spe. Diet, Spe. Foraging behav., Spe. Diet strat, Spe. Hab., Spe. Nest, Spe. Mean	Specialization respectively of diet, foraging behaviour, foraging substrate, habitat, nesting site and mean of five specializations	Morelli et al., 2020
Papilionidae	Wingspan	Average length of male wingspan in mm	Middleton-Welling et al., 2020
	FMoMean	Average duration of yearly flight period	
	HostplantN	Hostplant specificity, number of hostplants	
	HostplantSpe	Hostplant specificity index	Essens et al., 2017
	HPG	Hostplant growth form: Short herb/grass (<1 m) (Bi), tall herb/grass (>1 m) (Th), shrub (Sb), tree (Tr), liana (Li)	
	SSI	Species Specialization Index	Dupont et al., 2013
	AltVeg	Altitudinal vegetation: A=Anthropogenic, Co=Foothill, TheMeMed=Thermo/Meso-Mediterranean, Med=Mediterranean, SupMed=Supra-Mediterranean, Mo=Montane, ASa=Alpine and Subalpine	
Rarity	Rarity in France between 1 very rare to 3 common species	In Moussus et al., 2019 from oreina.org and faune.france.org	

The phylogenetic trees used to consider evolutionary relationships were from Jetz et al. (2012) and Wiemers et al. (2019, 2020) for the Aves and Papilionidae, respectively.

Appendix B - Supplementary results

B.1 - Description of observation databases (Local SINP, GBIF, Vigie Nature) available nine taxonomic groups in the three study sites (T1: Lodévois-Larzac, T2: Brocéliande, T3: La Rochelle) for “Local” (study site with a buffer zone 10 km), “Regional” (administrative region) and “Country” (continental France) scales. Statistics: “nSp” is the number of species with at least five observations on the study site within a 10 km buffer; “pSp<15obs”, “pSp15.50obs” and “pSp>50obs” are the percentage of species with <15, 15 to 50 and >50 observations respectively and “-” represents no data available.

B.1.A - Local scale (10km buffer zone).

Taxa	Statistic	Local									All databases combined		
		GBIF			SINP			Vigie Nature			T1	T2	T3
		T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3
Amphibia	nSp	11	1	11	13	2	0	No program			14	2	11
	pSp<15obs	82%	100%	100%	23%	50%	-				29%	50%	100%
	pSp15.50obs	18%	0%	0%	15%	50%	-				7%	50%	0%
	pSp>50obs	0%	0%	0%	62%	0%	-				64%	0%	0%
Aves	nSp	100	73	77	197	94	82	114	155	101	205	171	132
	pSp<15obs	87%	93%	95%	37%	96%	85%	56%	50%	54%	37%	47%	59%
	pSp15.50obs	10%	6%	4%	23%	3%	15%	32%	17%	20%	22%	22%	13%
	pSp>50obs	3%	1%	1%	40%	1%	0%	12%	33%	27%	41%	31%	28%
Chiroptera	nSp	4	0	5	21	6	18	25	22	24	26	22	26
	pSp<15obs	100%	-	100%	10%	83%	50%	12%	41%	21%	12%	41%	27%
	pSp15.50obs	0%	-	0%	38%	0%	44%	16%	36%	46%	19%	36%	34%
	pSp>50obs	0%	-	0%	52%	17%	6%	72%	23%	33%	69%	23%	39%
Flora	nSp	786	476	639	1703	1335	843	286	177	136	1844	1460	1093
	pSp<15obs	81%	85%	81%	52%	48%	74%	100%	100%	100%	52%	50%	72%
	pSp15.50obs	16%	14%	17%	30%	25%	14%	0%	0%	0%	28%	24%	17%
	pSp>50obs	3%	1%	3%	18%	27%	12%	0%	0%	0%	20%	25%	11%
Mammalia	nSp	10	1	14	23	7	30	No program			23	7	30
	pSp<15obs	100%	100%	100%	78%	86%	60%				74%	86%	57%
	pSp15.50obs	0%	0%	0%	17%	14%	20%				22%	14%	20%
	pSp>50obs	0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	20%				4%	0%	23%
Odonata	nSp	38	5	23	57	1	0	0	1	24	57	7	30
	pSp<15obs	74%	100%	100%	28%	100%	-	-	100%	100%	28%	100%	97%
	pSp15.50obs	26%	0%	0%	37%	0%	-	-	0%	0%	30%	0%	3%
	pSp>50obs	0%	0%	0%	35%	0%	-	-	0%	0%	42%	0%	0%
Orthoptera	nSp	53	3	24	91	8	0	25	19	19	98	25	34
	pSp<15obs	92%	100%	100%	71%	100%	-	24%	58%	16%	56%	68%	53%
	pSp15.50obs	8%	0%	0%	23%	0%	-	24%	32%	52%	18%	24%	29%
	pSp>50obs	0%	0%	0%	6%	0%	-	52%	10%	32%	26%	8%	18%
Papilionidae	nSp	115	15	33	154	11	0	0	0	50	154	18	52
	pSp<15obs	60%	100%	94%	21%	100%	-	-	-	88	21%	100%	73%
	pSp15.50obs	30%	0%	6%	19%	0%	-	-	-	12	18%	0%	27%
	pSp>50obs	10%	0%	0%	60%	0%	-	-	-	0	60%	0%	0%
Reptilia	nSp	18	2	7	21	4	0	No program			22	4	7
	pSp<15obs	67%	100%	100%	24%	100%	-				27%	75%	100%
	pSp15.50obs	28%	0%	0%	33%	0%	-				32%	25%	0%
	pSp>50obs	6%	0%	0%	43%	0%	-				41%	0%	0%

B.1.A - Regional scale.

Taxa	Statistic	GBIF			Regional Vigie Nature			All databases combined		
		T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3
Amphibia	nSp	13	2	11	No program			14	2	11
	pSp<15obs	8%	0%	73%				7%	0%	73%
	pSp15.50obs	23%	50%	18%				14%	50%	18%
	pSp>50obs	69%	50%	9%				79%	50%	9%
Aves	nSp	198	159	120	182	143	120	205	166	132
	pSp<15obs	21%	21%	40%	31%	29%	32%	12%	16%	19%
	pSp15.50obs	12%	12%	22%	21%	15%	27%	11%	10%	28%
	pSp>50obs	67%	67%	38%	48%	56%	41%	77%	74%	53%
Chiroptera	nSp	13	13	5	25	22	24	26	22	26
	pSp<15obs	100%	100%	100%	0%	0%	8%	0%	0%	15%
	pSp15.50obs	0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	17%	8%	0%	15%
	pSp>50obs	0%	0%	0%	96%	100%	75%	92%	100%	69%
Flora	nSp	1428	1093	825	825	657	413	1844	1158	1093
	pSp<15obs	43%	38%	47%	95%	94%	94%	32%	40%	47%
	pSp15.50obs	19%	19%	20%	5%	6%	6%	26%	19%	23%
	pSp>50obs	38%	49%	33%	0%	0%	0%	42%	41%	31%
Mammalia	nSp	23	6	21	No program			23	6	30
	pSp<15obs	39%	33%	62%				30%	33%	50%
	pSp15.50obs	26%	0%	33%				22%	0%	23%
	pSp>50obs	35%	67%	5%				48%	67%	27%
Odonata	nSp	56	7	28	56	7	27	57	7	30
	pSp<15obs	18%	14%	64%	77%	71%	100%	9%	14%	53%
	pSp15.50obs	30%	14%	25%	23%	29%	0%	21%	14%	37%
	pSp>50obs	52%	71%	11%	0%	0%	0%	70%	72%	10%
Orthoptera	nSp	93	25	26	25	19	19	98	25	34
	pSp<15obs	42%	24%	58%	4%	0%	11%	30%	4%	27%
	pSp15.50obs	39%	40%	42%	4%	0%	16%	22%	0%	29%
	pSp>50obs	19%	36%	0%	92%	100%	74%	48%	96%	44%
Papilionidae	nSp	144	18	43	132	18	51	154	18	52
	pSp<15obs	12%	0%	37%	42%	11%	55%	7%	0%	34%
	pSp15.50obs	19%	11%	42%	30%	22%	41%	13%	6%	31%
	pSp>50obs	69%	89%	21%	28%	67%	4%	81%	94%	35%
Reptilia	nSp	20	4	7	No program			22	4	7
	pSp<15obs	20%	0%	14%				18%	0%	14%
	pSp15.50obs	30%	25%	57%				28%	25%	57%
	pSp>50obs	50%	75%	29%				59%	75%	29%

B.1.C - Country scale.

Taxa	Statistic	GBIF			Country Vigie Nature			All databases combined		
		T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3
Amphibia	nSp	14	2	11	No program			14	2	11
	pSp<15obs	7%	0%	0%				0%	0%	0%
	pSp15.50obs	0%	0%	9%				7%	0%	9%
	pSp.>50obs	93%	100%	91%				93%	100%	91%
Aves	nSp	204	170	131	201	170	132	205	171	132
	pSp<15obs	2%	1%	1%	8%	9%	4%	1%	0%	0%
	pSp15.50obs	3%	1%	1%	11%	9%	7%	1%	1%	0%
	pSp.>50obs	95%	98%	98%	81%	82%	89%	98%	99%	100%
Chiroptera	nSp	19	19	21	25	22	25	26	22	26
	pSp<15obs	90%	89%	90%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4%
	pSp15.50obs	10%	11%	10%	0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	0%
	pSp.>50obs	0%	0%	0%	100%	100%	100%	96%	100%	96%
Flora	nSp	1573	1261	995	1336	1105	848	1844	1460	1093
	pSp<15obs	25%	20%	17%	68%	61%	53%	19%	14%	16%
	pSp15.50obs	18%	18%	16%	19%	23%	27%	21%	17%	16%
	pSp.>50obs	57%	62%	67%	13%	16%	20%	60%	69%	68%
Mammalia	nSp	23	6	28	No program			23	7	30
	pSp<15obs	13%	16%	18%				9%	14%	23%
	pSp15.50obs	17%	17%	28%				13%	29%	17%
	pSp.>50obs	70%	67%	54%				78%	57%	60%
Odonata	nSp	57	7	30	57	7	30	57	7	30
	pSp<15obs	2%	0%	0%	11%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	pSp15.50obs	10%	14%	0%	26%	0%	13%	3%	0%	0%
	pSp.>50obs	88%	86%	100%	63%	100%	87%	97%	100%	100%
Orthoptera	nSp	95	25	34	25	19	19	98	25	34
	pSp<15obs	22%	12%	6%	4%	0%	0%	15%	0%	0%
	pSp15.50obs	28%	20%	21%	0%	0%	0%	25%	4%	9%
	pSp.>50obs	50%	68%	73%	96%	100%	100%	60%	96%	91%
Papilionidae	nSp	147	18	52	149	18	52	154	18	52
	pSp<15obs	4%	0%	0%	13%	5%	0%	1%	0%	0%
	pSp15.50obs	8%	0%	0%	18%	6%	0%	7%	0%	0%
	pSp.>50obs	88%	100%	100%	69%	89%	100%	92%	100%	100%
Reptilia	nSp	21	4	7	No program			22	4	7
	pSp<15obs	0%	0%	0%				4%	0%	0%
	pSp15.50obs	14%	0%	0%				5%	0%	0%
	pSp.>50obs	86%	100%	100%				91%	100%	100%

B.2 - SDM evaluation of *Aves* and *Papilionidae* taxonomic groups for (A) three individual database sources and (B) between SDM using different pseudo-absence sources. Each graphic is a pair of databases (National combined GBIF and Vigie Nature). Each point is an individual species that is listed in both databases, some species are assessed only in one database (missing). A Boyce's index threshold of 0.3 is used to assess the proportion of satisfactory and unsatisfactory models conjointly for each of the two database sources. The blue quadrant contains species whose SDMs are evaluated in a satisfactory manner in both data bases (Boyce index > 0.3 for both databases); the red quadrant contains the species for which SDMs are evaluated in an unsatisfactory manner in both databases (Boyce index < 0.3 for both databases). In the top-left quadrant and the bottom-right quadrants, SDM model evaluation was satisfactory for only one database (on the in y and x axes respectively).

B.3 - Overlap between SDM from individual database sources. VN is Vigie Nature database and National combined GBIF and Vigie Nature.

B.4 - Overlap between SDM from individual database sources and SDM from mixed databases (i.e. using absence from Vigie Nature). National combine of GBIF and Vigie Nature.

B.5 - Maps of conservation planning area for Aves and Papilionidae of tree study sites (T1, T2, T3) from different individual database source (GBIF, Vigie Nature and "National databases" combining the two databases).

B.6 - Evaluation of the quality of the full model (*Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.*) compared to null model using AIC.

Model	Aves	Papilionidae
Full	3057	1322
Null	3357	1574

B.7 – Species list observed in each study site (T1, T2, T3) and their French status from TAXREF.V14 (Presence, Introduced, Invasive introduced) and IUCN regional red list from BD.STATUT.V16 (LC, NT, VU, EN, CR, DD, NA) for A) Aves species and B) Papilionidae Species.

B.7.A – Aves species

Species	Observed			French status	IUCN regional red list		
	T1	T2	T3		T1	T2	T3
<i>Accipiter gentilis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	VU	EN
<i>Accipiter nisus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Acrocephalus arundinaceus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	VU	CR	-
<i>Acrocephalus schoenobaenus</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	VU	LC
<i>Acrocephalus scirpaceus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NT	VU	-
<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	EN	CR	NA
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aegypius monachus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	CR	-	-
<i>Aix galericulata</i>	Yes	-	-	Introduced	NA	-	-
<i>Alauda arvensis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	VU	LC
<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	LC
<i>Alectoris rufa</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	DD	DD	DD
<i>Anas acuta</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	VU
<i>Anas crecca</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	LC
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	DD	LC	LC
<i>Anser anser</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	VU	NA
<i>Anthus campestris</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	VU	EN	-
<i>Anthus pratensis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	VU	EN	VU
<i>Anthus spinoletta</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	LC	LC
<i>Anthus trivialis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Apus apus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Aquila fasciata</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	CR	-	-
<i>Ardea alba</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	VU	NT	EN
<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	EN	VU	-
<i>Ardeola ralloides</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Asio otus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	LC	-
<i>Athene noctua</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	VU
<i>Aythya ferina</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	EN
<i>Aythya fuligula</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	LC
<i>Botaurus stellaris</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	EN	-	-
<i>Branta bernicla</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	NA	LC
<i>Bubo bubo</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	NT
<i>Burhinus oedicnemus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	NT	-
<i>Buteo buteo</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Calandrella brachydactyla</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	EN	-	-
<i>Calidris alba</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Calidris alpina</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Caprimulgus europaeus</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	LC	-	LC
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	VU	NT	LC
<i>Cecropis daurica</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Certhia familiaris</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Cettia cetti</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Charadrius alexandrinus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	EN	-
<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NT	VU	-
<i>Charadrius hiaticula</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	VU	VU	-
<i>Chlidonias niger</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NA	CR	-
<i>Chloris chloris</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	LC
<i>Chroicocephalus ridibundus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	VU	LC
<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NT	NT	-
<i>Ciconia nigra</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	EN	-	-
<i>Cinclus cinclus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Circaetus gallicus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	EN	-
<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	VU	VU	-
<i>Circus cyaneus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	EN	NT	EN
<i>Circus pygargus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	EN	NT	-
<i>Cisticola juncidis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Clamator glandarius</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	NT	-	-
<i>Coccothraustes coccothraustes</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	VU

<i>Columba livia</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	DD	DD	DD
<i>Columba oenas</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	VU	EN	LC
<i>Columba palumbus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coracias garrulus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	NT	-	-
<i>Corvus corax</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Corvus corone</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Corvus frugilegus</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	LC	LC
<i>Corvus monedula</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	VU	LC
<i>Cuculus canorus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cygnus olor</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NA	LC	-
<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Dendrocopos major</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Dendrocopos minor</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Dryocopus martius</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	LC	-	LC
<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	NT
<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	VU	-
<i>Emberiza calandra</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	VU	EN
<i>Emberiza cirius</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Emberiza citrinella</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	NT
<i>Emberiza hortulana</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Emberiza schoeniclus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	EN	EN	VU
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Falco columbarius</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Falco naumanni</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	VU	CR	-
<i>Falco subbuteo</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	NT
<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Falco vespertinus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NA	NA	-
<i>Ficedula albicollis</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	NT	-	-
<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	EN	-	-
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Fringilla montifringilla</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	DD
<i>Fulica atra</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Galerida cristata</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	LC	-
<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	CR	CR	NA
<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Grus grus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	CR	CR	-
<i>Gyps fulvus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Hieraaetus pennatus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	NT	-
<i>Hippolais polyglotta</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	LC
<i>Ichthyaetus melanocephalus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	CR	-
<i>Jynx torquilla</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NT	VU	-
<i>Lanius collurio</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	EN
<i>Lanius excubitor</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	NA
<i>Lanius meridionalis</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	EN	-	-
<i>Lanius senator</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	NT	-	-
<i>Larus argentatus</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	VU	VU
<i>Larus canus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	EN	-
<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NA	LC	LC
<i>Larus marinus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	EN	-
<i>Larus michahellis</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	VU	-
<i>Limosa lapponica</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Limosa limosa</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	CR	-
<i>Linaria cannabina</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT	LC
<i>Locustella luscinioides</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	EN	-
<i>Locustella naevia</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	DD	VU	LC
<i>Lophophanes cristatus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	VU	LC
<i>Loxia curvirostra</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Lullula arborea</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	VU
<i>Luscinia svecica</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	LC	-
<i>Mareca penelope</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	LC
<i>Mareca strepera</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	LC
<i>Mergus merganser</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	NA
<i>Merops apiaster</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NT	VU	-
<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	LC	-

<i>Milvus milvus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	EN	-	-
<i>Monticola saxatilis</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Monticola solitarius</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Motacilla alba</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	LC	-	LC
<i>Motacilla flava</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NT	LC	-
<i>Muscicapa striata</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Neophron percnopterus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	EN	-
<i>Numenius arquata</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	CR	EN	-
<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	NT	VU	-
<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	EN	EN
<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	LC	-
<i>Otus scops</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	NT	-	-
<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Parus major</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Passer domesticus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Passer montanus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	EN	EN
<i>Perdix perdix</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	DD	DD
<i>Periparus ater</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	LC	-	NT
<i>Pernis apivorus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	VU	-
<i>Petronia petronia</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NA	VU	LC
<i>Phasianus colchicus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Introduced	NA	DD	DD
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	VU
<i>Phylloscopus bonelli</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	NT	-
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Phylloscopus sibilatrix</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	EN	-	NT
<i>Phylloscopus trochilus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NA	CR	EN
<i>Pica pica</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Picus canus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	EN	CR	-
<i>Picus viridis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	EN	-
<i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>	-	-	Yes	Present	-	-	LC
<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Podiceps cristatus</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	LC	-	LC
<i>Poecile palustris</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	VU	NT
<i>Prunella collaris</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	EN	-	-
<i>Prunella modularis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Pyrhacorax pyrrhacorax</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Pyrrhula pyrrhula</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	VU	-	VU
<i>Rallus aquaticus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	VU	-
<i>Recurvirostra avosetta</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	VU	-
<i>Regulus ignicapilla</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Regulus regulus</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	LC	-	LC
<i>Riparia riparia</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	EN	NT	LC
<i>Saxicola rubetra</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	EN	CR	-
<i>Saxicola rubicola</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	VU	NT	LC
<i>Scolopax rusticola</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	DD	-	-
<i>Serinus serinus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Sitta europaea</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Spatula clypeata</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	DD	VU	LC
<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	CR	-
<i>Spinus spinus</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-
<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	VU	-
<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Streptopelia turtur</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	VU	LC
<i>Strix aluco</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	DD
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Sylvia borin</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Sylvia cantillans</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	LC	-
<i>Sylvia communis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Sylvia conspicillata</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	EN	-
<i>Sylvia hortensis</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Sylvia melanocephala</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	LC	-	-
<i>Sylvia undata</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	VU	-	LC
<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Tachymartia melba</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	VU	-	-

<i>Tadorna ferruginea</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	LC	LC	-
<i>Tetrax tetrax</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	NT	-	-
<i>Thalasseus sandvicensis</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	VU	NT	-
<i>Tichodroma muraria</i>	Yes	-	-	Present	CR	-	-
<i>Tringa erythropus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	NA	-
<i>Tringa ochropus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	NA	NA	DD
<i>Tringa totanus</i>	Yes	Yes	-	Present	EN	VU	-
<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Turdus iliacus</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	NA	-	DD
<i>Turdus merula</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Turdus philomelos</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Turdus pilaris</i>	Yes	-	Yes	Present	VU	-	DD
<i>Turdus torquatus</i>	-	Yes	-	Present	-	LC	-
<i>Turdus viscivorus</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT	LC
<i>Tyto alba</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	VU	DD
<i>Upupa epops</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC	LC
<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	-	Yes	Yes	Present	-	VU	VU

B.7.A – Papilionidae species

Species	Observed		French status	IUCN regional red list	
	T1	T3		T1	T3
<i>Aglais io</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Anthocharis euphenoides</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Apatura ilia</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Apatura iris</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	NT
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT
<i>Aporia crataegi</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Araschnia levana</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Arethusana arethusa</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Argynnis pandora</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Argynnis paphia</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Aricia agestis</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Aricia montensis</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Boloria dia</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Boloria euphrosyne</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Boloria selene</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Brenthis daphne</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Brenthis hecate</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Brintesia circe</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Cacyreus marshalli</i>	Yes	-	Invasive introduced	NA	-
<i>Callophrys avis</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Callophrys rubi</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Carcharodus alceae</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Charaxes jasius</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Chazara briseis</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Coenonympha arcania</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha dorus</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Colias alfacariensis</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Colias crocea</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Cupido alcetas</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Cupido argiades</i>	-	Yes	Present	-	NT
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Cupido osiris</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT
<i>Erebia aethiops</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Erebia epistygne</i>	Yes	-	Present	EN	-
<i>Erebia meolans</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Erebia neoridas</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Erynnis tages</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Euchloe crameri</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Euphydryas aurinia</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Fabriciana adippe</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Fabriciana niobe</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-

<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Glaucopsyche melanops</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Gonepteryx cleopatra</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Gonepteryx rhamni</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Hamearis lucina</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Hesperia comma</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Hipparchia alcyone</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Hipparchia fagi</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Hipparchia fidia</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia genava</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Hipparchia semele</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	EN
<i>Hipparchia statilinus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	EN
<i>Hyponephele lupina</i>	Yes	-	Present	EN	-
<i>Hyponephele lycaon</i>	Yes	-	Present	EN	-
<i>Iberochloe tagis</i>	Yes	-	Present	EN	-
<i>Iphiclides podalirius</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Issoria lathonia</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Laeosopsis roboris</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Lampides boeticus</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Lasiommata maera</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	CR
<i>Lasiommata megera</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Leptidea sinapis</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Leptotes pirithous</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Libythea celtis</i>	Yes	-	Introduced	LC	-
<i>Limenitis camilla</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Limenitis reducta</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Lycaena alciphron</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Lycaena dispar</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Lycaena phlaeas</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Lycaena tityrus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Lysandra bellargus</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Lysandra coridon</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Lysandra hispana</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Melanargia galathea</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Melanargia lachesis</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Melanargia occitanica</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Melanargia russiae</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Melitaea athalia</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Melitaea celadussa</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Melitaea cinxia</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea deione</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Melitaea diamina</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Melitaea didyma</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Melitaea parthenoides</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Melitaea phoebe</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Minois dryas</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Muschampia floccifera</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Muschampia lavatherae</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Muschampia proto</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Papilio machaon</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Pararge aegeria</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Parnassius apollo</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Phengaris arion</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Pieris brassicae</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Pieris mannii</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Pieris napi</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Pieris rapae</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Plebejus argus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	NT
<i>Plebejus idas</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	NT	CR
<i>Polygonia c-album</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Polyommatus daphnis</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Polyommatus dolus</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Polyommatus dorylas</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Polyommatus escheri</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC

<i>Polyommatus thersites</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Pontia daplidice</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Pseudophilotes baton</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Pyrgus alveus</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Pyrgus armoricanus</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Pyrgus carthami</i>	Yes	-	Present	NT	-
<i>Pyrgus cirsii</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Pyrgus foulquieri</i>	Yes	-	Present	EN	-
<i>Pyrgus malvae</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Pyrgus malvoides</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Pyrgus onopordi</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Pyronia bathseba</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Pyronia cecilia</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Pyronia tithonus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Quercusia quercus</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Satyrium acaciae</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Satyrium esculi</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Satyrium ilicis</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Satyrium pruni</i>	Yes	-	Present	DD	-
<i>Satyrium spini</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Satyrium w-album</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Satyrus actaea</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Satyrus ferula</i>	Yes	-	Present	VU	-
<i>Speyeria aglaja</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Spialia sertorius</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Thecla betulae</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Thymelicus acteon</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Thymelicus lineola</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Thymelicus sylvestris</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Vanessa atalanta</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	Yes	Yes	Present	LC	LC
<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-
<i>Zerynthia rumina</i>	Yes	-	Present	LC	-